

The prevalence of some psychoactive substances use among secondary school adolescents in Bosso Local Government Area, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of some psychoactive substances use was investigated among secondary school adolescents in Bosso Local Government Area, Niger State, Nigeria by descriptive cross-sectional survey design. Data from self-administered Psychoactive Substance Abuse Questionnaire (PSAQ) were analysed, using appropriate statistics. Amongst one thousand seven hundred and nineteen (1719) valid (of the one thousand eight hundred and twenty, 1820) respondents responses, their use for coffee (1028 or 59.8%) and kola nuts (957 or 55.7%) were highly accepted while that for petrol (568 or 33.0%) was moderately accepted. Their substance use response for cigarette (462 or 26.9%) followed by marijuana (449 or 26.1%), codeine/cough syrup (402 or 23.4%), alcohol (395 or 23.0%), caffeine (251 or 14.6%), paints (227 or 13.2%), sleeping pills (217 or 12.6%), cannabis (196 or 11.4%), amphetamine (190 or 11.1%) and gasoline (188 or 10.9%) was lowly accepted. Their least self-reported substance use for opium (1 or 0.1%) followed by valium (29 or 1.7%), Lysergic acid diethylamide, LSD, or solution (59 or 3.4%), glue (71 or 4.1%) and cocaine (89 or 5.2%) were not accepted. The result established the prevalent use of these common substances, with coffee, kola nuts and petrol seemingly serving as the gateway substances, among the studied adolescents. This study may have significant public health implications, warranting biochemical indicators assessment of the substances-induced toxicity in these adolescents to provide further basis for prevention and policy formulation programs. Regular counseling and enlightenment of the adolescents on the consequences of substance use are required, hence recommended.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Generally, substance use predates modern history while substances abuse constitutes a major sociological ill habit with adverse public health implications. Psychoactive substances could modify the perceptions, moods, behaviours and physical/psychological functions of such users [1]. Agent-induced toxic effects have been documented [2-6], implying that the possible toxic implications of such substances abuse could compound the known psychoactive effects. Thus, psychoactive substance use, especially among adolescents, is a major public health and social concern.

Substance use is widespread in many African countries [7], including Nigeria with alcohol and tobacco acting as "gateway drugs" to life use of other substances [8]. Adolescence generally refers to individuals between the ages of 10-19 years. High rates of substance abuse in student populations have been reported [9-12]. Secondary school is unique in having the high number of teenagers who are seemingly battling with self identity and peer pressure influence. These make them more vulnerable to undertaking even illicit actions [13-14]. The study aimed to determine some psychoactive substances use among adolescents in Bosso Local Government Area (LGA) in Niger State, Nigeria, using descriptive cross-sectional survey

design method. Generally, most studies on substances use assess the prevalence of one or two psychoactive substance(s) at a time. The study could be achieved through the objective of answering the research question: What are the common psychoactive substances used among adolescents in Bosso LGA of Niger State? The result of this study could establish the prevalent use of some substances, and the possible "gateway" substance(s), among the secondary school adolescents in Bosso LGA, Nigeria. This study may provide further basis for substances abuse prevention and policy formulation programs.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was carried out between 2009 and 2011 as a Masters of Science degree research in the Department of Health and Physical Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Ethical approval and permission were sought and obtained from the Ethical Committee of the Department and the University. The students were informed about the purpose of the study. Consenting students were assured of their safety and confidential use of the outcome for research purpose. Descriptive cross-sectional survey research design was utilized which generally facilitates the description of a situation in its current state and gathers information directly from the subjects. This design was considered appropriate, as it has been used in related studies [15-16].

2.1 Population of the study and sample size determination

The population for the study consisted of all the secondary school adolescents in the twenty one (21) public schools in Bosso LGA, Niger State. Thus, the total population, comprising both males and females, was thirty four thousand four hundred and thirty one (34,431) students as at 2010 as ascertained from the Department of Planning and Statistics, Niger State Ministry of Education, Minna, Niger State.

The sample size for the study, $n = 1,820$, was determined by the multistage sampling procedure. This procedure involved stratifying the fourteen communities where the twenty one schools in Bosso LGA were sited into urban and rural and using the simple random sampling technique to select ten urban and three rural schools, making thirteen schools. The next stage involved cluster sampling of the thirteen schools into junior and senior classes and selected all to twenty six intact classes. With estimated class size of seventy (70) adolescents based on the information obtained from the Niger State Ministry of Education in the Department of Planning and Statistics, Minna Niger State, the sample size for the urban and rural schools was one thousand four hundred (1,400) and four hundred and twenty (420) adolescents, respectively. This summed up to a total sample size of one thousand eight hundred and twenty (1820) adolescents for the survey.

2.2. Instrument for data collection, its validity and reliability

The instrument used for data collection, Psychoactive Substance Abuse Questionnaire (PSAQ) was developed in the course of the study and validated by five (5) experts. Three (3) of the experts were in the Health and Physical Education Department while one (1) each was in the Measurement and Evaluation Department and Educational Psychology Department, all in the University of Nigeria Nsukka. The objectives of the study and research question(s) accompanied the questionnaire to enable the validators determine whether the contents were in line with the objectives of the study. The questionnaire items were structured to supply the substances used among the secondary school adolescents out of eighteen listed psychoactive substances. The respondents were requested to mark [X] in as many options as are applicable to them.

The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering twenty copies of the structured questionnaire twenty secondary school adolescents in Chanchaga LGA of Niger State under close examination. Their responses to the question were scrutinized and found to be devoid of any bias, indicating that questionnaire was quite understandable and usable, hence reliable for this study.

2.3 Access to data collection

Access to data collection was gained using the letter of introduction duly signed by the Head, Department of Health and Physical Education, University of Nigeria Nsukka which was presented to the respective school Principals for permission to access the students. The researcher, with the assistance of some class teachers, administered copies of the questionnaire to the consenting students and ensured that there was no exchange of idea while filling the questionnaire. The filled questionnaires were retrieved on the spot, ensuring hundred percent (100%) questionnaire return rate.

2.4 Extent/rate of abuse decision range

To determine the extent/rate of substance use, the following percentage range structure and corresponding interpretation were developed and used *viz*: 80%, very highly accepted/abused (VHA); 50-79%, highly accepted/abused (HA); 30-49%, moderately accepted/abused (MA); 10-29%, lowly accepted/abused (LA) and 0-9%, not accepted/abused (NA). Out of 1820 copies of the questionnaire that were distributed, filled and collected (returned), one hundred and one (101) copies were discarded for incomplete filling, and the remaining 1719 copies were utilized and served as the effective sample size for the study.

2.5 Data analysis

The data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences [SPSS] for Windows version 16.0 and the result presented based on simple percent and frequency.

3. RESULTS

The percentage of analysis of psychoactive substance commonly used by adolescents in the surveyed secondary schools were presented in Tables 1,2 and 3. The result revealed that amongst one thousand seven hundred and nineteen (1719) valid (of the one thousand eight hundred and twenty, 1820) respondents responses, their use for coffee (1028 or 59.8%) and kolanuts (957 or 55.7%) were highly

accepted/abused while that for petrol (568 or 33.0%) was moderately accepted/abused.

The reported substance use for cigarette (462 or 26.9%) followed by marijuana (449 or 26.1%), codeine/cough syrup (402 or 23.4%), alcohol (395 or 23.0%), caffeine (251 or 14.6%), paints (227 or 13.2%), sleeping pills (217 or 12.6%), cannabis (196 or 11.4), amphetamine (190 or 11.1%) and gasoline (188 or 10.9%) was lowly accepted. The least reported substance use among the secondary school adolescents for opium (1 or 0.1%) followed by valium (29 or 1.7%), Lysergic acid diethylamide, LSD, or solution (59 or 3.4%), glue (71 or 4.1%) and cocaine (89 or 5.2%) were not accepted/abused.

Table 1. Percentage Analysis of alcohol, marijuana, cigarette, cocaine, valium and sleeping pills as accepted/abused by the adolescents (n= 1719).

Substances abused	Statistics	Response		Total	Decision
		No	Yes		
Alcohol(Giya)	Frequency	1324	395	1719	LA
	Percent	77.0	23.0	100	
Marijuana (We we)	Frequency	1279	449	1719	LA
	Percent	73.9	26.1	100	
Cigarette (Taba)	Frequency	1257	462	1719	LA
	Percent	73.1	26.9	100	
Cocaine	Frequency	1630	89	1719	NA
	Percent	94.8	5.2	100	
Valium	Frequency	1690	29	1719	NA
	Percent	98.3	1.7	100	
Sleeping pills	Frequency	1502	217	1719	LA
	Percent	87.4	12.6	100	

Note: LA: low acceptance/abuse, NA: no acceptance/abuse, MA: moderate acceptance/abuse, HA: high acceptance/abuse

Table 2. Percentage analysis of glue, paint, kolanuts, codeine/cough syrup, petrol and gasoline as accepted/abused by the adolescents (n= 1719).

Substances abused	Statistics	Response		Total	Decision
		No	Yes		
Glue	Frequency	1648	71	1719	NA
	Percent	95.9	4.1	100	
Paints	Frequency	1492	227	1719	LA
	Percent	86.8	13.2	100	
Kolanuts (Goro)	Frequency	762	957	1719	HA
	Percent	44.3	55.7	100	
Codeine/cough syrup	Frequency	1317	402	1719	LA
	Percent	76.6	23.4	100	
Petrol	Frequency	1151	568	1719	MA
	Percent	67.0	33.0	100	
Gasoline	Frequency	1530	188	1719	LA
	Percent	89.1	10.9	100	

Note: LA: low acceptance/abuse, NA: no acceptance/abuse, MA: moderate acceptance/abuse, HA: high acceptance/abuse

Table 3. Percentage analysis of opium, LSD, cannabis, coffee, caffeine and amphetamine as accepted/abused by the adolescents (n= 1719).

Substances abused	Statistics	Response		Total	Decision
		No	Yes		
Opium	Frequency	1718	1	1719	NA
	Percent	99.9	0.1	100	
Lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD) (Solution)	Frequency	1660	59	1719	NA
	Percent	96.6	3.4	100	
Cannabis	Frequency	1523	196	1719	LA
	Percent	88.6	11.4	100	
Coffee	Frequency	691	1028	1719	HA
	Percent	40.2	59.8	100	
Caffeine	Frequency	1468	251	1719	LA
	Percent	85.4	14.6	100	
Amphetamine	Frequency	1529	190	1719	LA
	Percent	88.9	11.1	100	

Note: LA: low acceptance/abuse, NA: no acceptance/abuse, MA: moderate acceptance/abuse, HA: high acceptance/abuse

4. DISCUSSION

The prevalence of some psychoactive substances use was investigated among secondary school adolescents in Bosso Local Government Area, Niger State, Nigeria by cross-sectional survey design. Interestingly, none of the substances had use response rate of 80% and above implying that none of these substances was very highly accepted or abused. The prevalence range in this study (0.1% - 59.8%) is comparable to 1.3% - 30.0% reported [17] for adolescents in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria, but not to the range (0.3% - 12.5%) reported [18] for those in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. The prevalence range obtained in this study is unique as it represented that of many common psychoactive substances, hence may be significant in public health decision making and in planning for correction, counsel, control and prevention programs for these substances use.

Alcohol was the most highly used psychoactive substance amongst adolescents in previous similar epidemiological studies in other parts of Nigeria [18;19;20;21]. In contrast, result of this study revealed that the use of coffee (1028 or 59.8%) followed by kola nuts (957 or 55.7%) were mostly used or highly accepted/abused among the adolescents while their use for petrol (568 or 33.0%) was moderate or moderately accepted/abused. This is not surprising since Bosso is located in the northern part of Nigeria. Alcohol is available and accessible even to adolescent in other parts, unlike in the northern part, of the country. Thus, the secondary school adolescents in Bosso probably resorted to the use of coffee, kola nuts and to a lesser extent petrol that may be readily available and accessible to them. Similarly, the moderate use response implying and moderate acceptance/abuse for petrol among the students may be related to its availability and ease of procurement. In particular, the high use and acceptance for coffee and kola nuts may be related their use by students as stimulants (to stay awake) [8;22]. Such use for coffee and kola nuts however should be discouraged as the

substances could serve as gateway to life time psychoactive substances use [8;23] with the attendant general risks of adverse effects.

The studied adolescents self reported low substance use, hence low acceptance/abuse decision, were as presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3. The recorded response use for marijuana and cigarette were similar, apparently indicating associated use for these psychoactive substances among the secondary school adolescents. The adolescents use response for cigarette (462 or 26.9%) compared with that reported earlier, but not in Nigeria, by Kwamanga, *et al.* [24] and Peltzer [25]. However, this relatively low use response for cigarette was remarkably higher than 1.5% and 2.7% respectively reported by Adelekan, *et al.* [17] and Anochie and Nkanginieme [18]. This is particularly worrisome, warranting urgent control intervention especially with their possible associated use for cigarette and marijuana suggested in this study.

The self reported substance use for opium (1 or 0.1%), valium (29 or 1.7%), LSD (59 or 3.4%), glue (71 or 4.1%) and cocaine (89 or 5.2%) were low, hence not accepted/abused. The result was not surprising since, for instance, opium, apart from being inaccessible, is very expensive, and valium, though common, is a controlled drug hence not readily accessible. Generally, LSD (Lysergic acid diethylamide) is harmful which could deter the adolescent from its use, and perceived harmfulness had inverse relationship with substance use [26]. The low use response for cocaine (5.2%) agreed with that from previous study [27], though among medical students in Enugu state. This may be related to either the known risks from cocaine use among the respondents [26] or inaccessibility and high cost of cocaine.

5. CONCLUSION

The result established the prevalent use of these common psychoactive substances, with the highly accepted/abused (coffee and kola nuts) the moderately accepted/abused (petrol)

seemingly serving as the gateway substances, among the studied adolescents. This study may have significant public health implications, warranting biochemical indicators assessment of the substances-induced toxic effects in these adolescents to provide extent of use/abuse and further basis for correction, counsel and control planning. Regular counseling and enlightenment of the secondary school adolescents and in the area on the consequences of substance use and possible abuse are required, hence recommended to forestall their life time use of these and other psychoactive substances.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

EACC approved the version and interpreted the data to be published, EONC carried out the study and managed the literature searches under supervision while SES developed the concepts, designed the experiments and supervised the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All authors hereby declare that all experiments have been examined and approved by the appropriate ethics committee and have therefore been performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki.

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